

Lived Experiences of Child in Conflict with the Law During Rehabilitation

**Albito, Jeric P¹, Evangelista, Lovely Joy C², Matias, Nikka Joy S³, Rosales, Angelo Dave S⁴,
Tinguha, Daniel S⁵, Vengazo, Alejandro L⁶, and Fajardo, John Jerico C⁷**

Abstract

This study explored the lived experiences of five (5) male Children in Conflict with the Law (CICL) during their rehabilitation at Bahay Pag-Asa using a phenomenological research design. Participants, mostly 15 years old and in the facility for six months, were purposively selected. Data were gathered through interviews, coded, and analyzed using thematic analysis. The most difficult challenges they faced were homesickness and shame, highlighting the crucial role of family in their emotional well-being. Participants expressed regret over their actions, showing that repentance will always be in the latter part. Their accounts revealed that children have vulnerable emotions and often lack awareness of the consequences of their actions. To manage their situation, participants engaged in interpersonal relationship, recreational activities, and faith-based activities. These coping strategies helped ease their emotional burden. Relationships with fellow youth reduced isolation, as they shared similar experiences and challenges. The study emphasized the importance of sports as an outlet of emotion, helping release stress, promote well-being, and offer enjoyment. Meanwhile, faith-based activities allowed them to share personal struggles and served as a source of hope and guidance. The presence of social workers and peers provided strong support systems. Social workers offered not only basic needs but also emotional and psychological assistance. Peers helped lessen loneliness and created a sense of solidarity, uplifting one another during times of distress. The rehabilitation journey resulted in personal growth, companionship, and aspirations. Participants developed discipline, learned to value trust, and found healthier ways to connect with others. Though trust was hard to rebuild, Bahay Pag-Asa showed its importance in building relationships. Lastly, the experience influenced their future aspirations, with education seen as a stepping stone toward a better life. Despite their past, they remained hopeful for change.

Keywords: Homesickness, Shame, Interpersonal Relationship, Recreational Activities, Faith-based Activities, Personal Growth, Companionship, Aspiration

Introduction

Under Republic Act No. 9344 or the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act of 2006, a child is defined as anyone below 18 years old. A CICL is a child who is alleged, accused, or judged to have committed an offense under Philippine law. The law was created to protect the rights of children, especially those involved in crimes, and aims to remove the label of being a "criminal" from them. According to Idris et al. (2022), the defenseless nature of children has raised concerns in society, especially with the rise of crimes involving minors. Children are not only victims of crimes but also, at times, become the perpetrators. This growing concern has sparked debates, as children are heavily protected by law. Garcia and Williams (2023) explained that, unlike adult offenders, children do not have the same legal rights like posting bail or having a trial by jury. Instead, intervention programs are created for those aged 15 to below 18 since they are not yet criminally responsible for their actions.

To oversee the implementation of the law, the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Council (JJWC) was formed. The law requires that Local Government Units (LGUs) provide at least three years of rehabilitation for CICLs. As stated in Section 44 of RA 9344, the goal is to help CICLs reintegrate into society through programs that develop their social skills, education, emotional strength, and vocational abilities. These efforts prepare them for a stable future and help them heal from past trauma. In San Jose City, Nueva Ecija, a facility called Bahay Pag-Asa houses 13 male CICLs. This is concerning, especially since children are often seen as the "hope of the nation," as emphasized by Dr. Jose Rizal. Former Senate President Vicente Sotto III has proposed lowering the age of criminal responsibility to 12 due to increasing crimes committed by minors. However, Senator Joel Villanueva opposed this, saying that the problem lies in the system itself, not in the children. He suggested increasing penalties for adults who use children in crimes and improving intelligence and law enforcement capacity.

This study aims to understand the experiences of CICLs during rehabilitation, as this is the most critical phase in their journey. It is when they face challenges, receive support, and begin to change. The findings can help improve rehabilitation programs and juvenile justice policies in the Philippines.

Methods and Procedure

This study was guided by Republic Act No. 9344, the Juvenile Justice and Welfare Act of 2006, and its amendment, RA No. 10630, which focus on the rehabilitation of Children in Conflict with the Law (CICL) rather than punishment. The study used a qualitative, phenomenological research design to understand the real-life experiences of CICLs during rehabilitation. An interview guide with five parts was used to gather data, covering participants' background, challenges, coping strategies, support systems, and how rehabilitation impacted their behavior and mindset. Five male CICLs, selected through purposive sampling, participated. Ethical considerations were met by ensuring informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation. The data were collected after securing approval from the Department of Social Welfare and Development (DSWD) in San Jose City, Nueva Ecija. The interviews were transcribed and analyzed using thematic analysis to identify common patterns in the CICLs' experiences.

Results and Discussions

Participants' Background Information

Most of the Participants were 15 years old and had been in the Bahay Pag-Asa for six (6) months.

Challenges during rehabilitation

Two themes (2) were identified by the researchers from the responses of the participants. The challenges that the CICL faced during the rehabilitation were categorized into: homesickness and shame.

Homesickness

Many participants shared that being away from their families was the hardest part of staying in the rehabilitation center. They felt sad, lonely, and found it hard to adjust to a new environment. Participant 1 said, “Nakakainip tapos nakakalungkot po na hindi na namin kasama iyong mga magulang namin. Panibagong adjustment na naman po at bagong environment.” (It is boring and sad that we are no longer with our parents... It is another adjustment and a new environment.) Participant 4 shared, “Kalungkutan. Dahil malayo ako sa amin. Tuwing Biyernes ay mayroon po kaming family visitation, iyon po ang pinaka-hinihintay kong araw sa buong isang linggo... kaya dinadaan ko nalang sa pagsusulat ng kanta, at paggi-gitara.”

(Sadness. Because I am far from home. Every Friday we have family visitation, which I look forward to the most. I express my feelings through writing songs and playing the guitar.) Participant 5 expressed, “Pinakamahirap na naranasan ko ay malayo sa pamilya at hindi sila makasama sa New Year. Malungkot kasi malayo sa pamilya ko.” (The hardest thing I experienced was being away from my family and not spending New Year with them... It’s sad being far from my family.) These stories show that homesickness is a major emotional challenge for CICLs, especially because they are still young and emotionally dependent on their families. According to Urbano et al. (2023), homesickness is the emotional stress CICLs feel when they are away from familiar surroundings and loved ones. It can be caused by culture shock, new responsibilities, or loneliness. Staff should look out for signs of homesickness and help CICLs adjust by allowing them to talk, make friends, and feel supported.

Shame

Aside from homesickness, many participants felt ashamed of their actions. They shared feelings of regret and embarrassment, especially toward their families. Participant 2 said, “Siyempre po sa magulang lalo na at may family problem... Nahiya po ako sa mga magulang ko sa nagawa ko.” (Of course, especially for my parents since we have family problems. I felt ashamed of what I did.) Participant 3 added, “Mga pagsisisi at pagkakamali, tapos iisipin ang plano kung paano makakabawi sa mga tumutulong sa kalagayan ko.”(Regret for my mistakes, then I think about how to make it up to the people helping me.) These responses show that CICLs often feel guilt and remorse once they realize the consequences of their actions. They want to change and make things right, but the shame they carry can be heavy. According to Valenty (2021), being labeled as a “criminal” or “delinquent” can damage a young person’s self-esteem. This is linked to the labeling theory, which suggests that people tend to see themselves the way others see them. When society uses harsh labels, CICLs may feel worthless, making it harder for them to recover.

Treating them with understanding instead of judgment can help rebuild their confidence and support their rehabilitation.

Coping Mechanisms During Rehabilitation

Three (3) themes were identified by the researchers from the responses of the participants. The coping mechanisms that the CICL used during rehabilitation were categorized into: interpersonal relationship, recreational activities, and faith-based activities.

Interpersonal Relationship

Most participants said they build bonds with fellow youth residents to pass the time. Participant 1 shared, “Makikipag-biruan po o kaya makikipag-kulitan, makikipag-kuwentuhan gano’n po ang ginagawa ko para pampalipas oras.” Participant 2 said, “Nakikisama nalang po at nakiki-bonding nalang po sa mga kasama dito.” Participant 4 mentioned, “Nililibang ko din sarili ko sa pamamagitan ng pagbabasa at pakikipag-kuwentuhan sa mga kasama ko.” These interactions help lessen the feeling of being alone since they go through similar situations. As Hurst (2023) explained, social relationships help children develop skills in handling conflicts and give them emotional support. This shows that forming connections with others plays an important role in coping and maintaining emotional well-being.

Recreational Activities

Most participants said that doing recreational activities like basketball and chess helps them cope. Participant 5 shared, “Naglalaro ng basketball sa hapon at naglalaro ng chess, sa gabi naman bago matulog nagbabasa ako ng libro.” Another said, “Nagba-basketball sa hapon pero depende sa bantay kung papayagan.” Participant 3 stated, “Parang nasa bahay lang din. Pagluluto at pagbabasketball sa labas kapag walang nagaganap na problema sa amin.” Participant 2 added, “Gitara po tiyaka keyboard, mahilig po kasi ako sa music at instruments.” These activities help them release stress, feel better, and enjoy their time at Bahay Pag-Asa. According to Urbano et al. (2023), recreational activities like sports improve the physical and mental health of CICLs and help them build friendships and life skills. This shows that giving them time for sports and hobbies is important for their healing and growth.

Faith-Based Activities

Most participants shared that Bible study helped improve their well-being. Participant 1 said, “Dati po nag ba-bible study po kami tuwing Miyerkules, marami din po kaming natutunan doon.” Participant 2 added, “Minsan po may pastor din po na dumadalaw at nakakatulong po sa akin iyong Bible study para po mag-open po ng problema.” These faith-based activities helped them open up about personal problems and gave them guidance and hope. According to Solmayor and Embornas (2024), Bible study helps CICLs develop good values, self-discipline, and strong moral character. This shows that spiritual activities play an important role in helping them reflect, grow, and find a sense of purpose in life.

Support System During Rehabilitation

Two (2) themes were identified by the researchers from the responses of the participants. The support systems that were available to the CICL were categorized into: social workers and peers.

Availability of Social Workers

Most participants shared that the presence of social workers inside the rehabilitation center made them feel supported. Participant 1 said, “Sila Sir Wylo po tapos iyong mga social workers po. Iyong mga social worker po na nandito kasi po komportable po ako sa kanila. Naaayos po nila iyong problema namin kapag sinasabi namin sakanila.” Participant 2 also mentioned, “Kay Sir Wylo po tiyaka sa mga staff po na nandito. Kapag nagsasabi po ako sakanila gumagaan po iyong pakiramdam ko.” They see social workers as people they can trust and open up to. Participant 4 shared, “Iyong mga social worker, naranasan ko humingi ng tulong sa kanila tulad ng pagtatanong sa mga bagay-bagay dito tulad ng mga gawain at paano iyong mga patakaran dito.” Similarly, Participant 5 stated, “Sir Wylo kasi siya yung tumutulong sa akin kapag nalulungkot at namimiss ko pamilya ko. Nagiging komportable ako ‘pag kausap ko si Sir Wylo at gumagaan ang aking pakiramdam.” Social workers help fill the emotional gap caused by limited family interaction. According to Drobac and Najman (2021), facility personnel must act like parents to meet the emotional, physical, and social needs of CICLs. This helps build trust, communication, and a safe space for growth. Their presence plays a big role in making the CICLs feel valued and supported, which is important for their positive development.

Availability of Peers

Most participants mentioned that their peers helped them with various challenges. Participants 3 and 4 view their peers as a source of comfort because they shared similar experiences. "Kasamang pinaka-matagal dito, magtatanong ng problema kung napag-daanan niya ba at paano niya nalampasan." Participant 3 (I ask those who have been here the longest about my problems—if they've experienced the same and how they got through it). "Ang madalas kong kausap at lapitan ay ang mga ka-kuwarto ko lang din, dahil pare-parehas lang din kami ng pinagdadaan dito." Participant 4 (I usually talk to and approach my roommates because we are all going through the same things here). They see their peers as a support system during rehabilitation. Their peers helped ease their loneliness and created a sense of solidarity, allowing them to lift each other up during tough times. According to Reeta (2020), having supportive friends boosts a child's self-esteem, confidence, morale, values, and sense of community. On the other hand, bad company can have a negative effect and may even lead to involvement in harmful behavior.

Influences of Rehabilitation to CICLs Mindset and Behavior

Three (3) themes were identified by the researchers from the responses of the participants. The influence of rehabilitation to the mindset and attitude of CICL were categorized into: personal growth, companionship, and aspirations.

Personal Growth

The rehabilitation process helped the participants grow personally. Most of them shared that they learned to be polite and wake up early. Participant 1 said that he wakes up early to exercise and help with the chores, “Opo, natutunan ko pong gumalang, natuto rin po akong gumising nang maaga para mag exercise tapos gumawa po ng mga gawaing bahay kagaya po ng paglilinis at

paglalaba” (Yes, I learned to be respectful. I also learned to wake up early for exercise and to do household chores like cleaning and laundry). On the other hand, Participant 4 mentioned, “Maraming nagbago sa akin tulad ng paggising ko nang maaga at paggawa sa mga gawaing bahay” (So much has changed in me, like waking up early and helping with household chores). Participant 5 also mentioned that they learned how to cook dishes, “Natutunan kong magluto” (I learned how to cook). Rehabilitation teaches discipline and responsibility. Participants learned to do household chores and wake up early for physical exercise. According to Urbano et.al (2023), the programs in rehabilitation facilities offer opportunities for personal growth, skill development, and improved self-esteem. Through involvement in household chores and participation in center activities, CICLs gained a stronger sense of accountability and responsibility. These programs helped develop positive behaviors and attitudes, supporting CICLs' successful reintegration into society.

Companionship

Most participants shared that rehabilitation helped them learn how to be friendly and understand the importance of camaraderie. Participant 1 and 2 mentioned that they learned to socialize with other youth residents. “Tapos, marunong na rin po akong makipag-kaibigan dito” Participant 1 (I also learned how to make friends here). “Natutunan ko pong makisama sa mga kasama ko dito” Participant 2 (I learned how to get along with people here). They also found better ways to form friendships. Although it was difficult for them to trust others because of their past experiences, Bahay Pag-Asa taught them that trust is key in building relationships. Rendaje et.al (2024) found that children's daily interactions with each other can shape their social identity. They learn by combining their past experiences with new information. Juvenile offenders are influenced by both their personal traits and the environment, which plays a crucial role in shaping their behavior and how they view their experiences.

Aspirations

Most participants recognized the importance of education in achieving their goals. Participant 1 and 3 expressed their desire to continue their studies and become soldiers. “Sa ngayon po nagtutuloy parin po ako sa pag-aaral at gusto ko pong maging sundalo ‘pag tanda ko” (For now, I am continuing my studies and I want to be a soldier someday). Participant 2 wants to study criminology because his family depends on him. “Mag-aaral na po ako nang maigi kasi ako lang po iyong inaasahan ng pamilya ko lalo at ako po iyong panganay. Paglabas ko po gusto ko pong maging criminology student” (I will study hard because my family relies on me, especially since I am the eldest). Participant 4 and 5 also shared their aspirations of continuing their studies and helping their families. The rehabilitation process encouraged them to believe that education is key to achieving their dreams, despite their current challenges. According to Solmayor and Embornas (2024), aspirations give CICLs a sense of purpose and motivate them toward positive change.

Conclusion

With the foregoing findings, the researchers concluded the following: Participants' age were fall mostly under 15 years old. Majority of them were already six (6) months in the Bahay Pag-Asa. The most difficult challenge that CICLs faced during rehabilitation were homesickness and shame. They missed their families and the way they lived before rehabilitation. They also felt ashamed especially for their family for what they did. Therefore, family is a big factor contributing to emotional well-being of CICLs. They perceived recreational activities, interpersonal relationships, and faith-based activities as their coping mechanism. They found these factors as a

way to cope to their present situation. It highlighted the importance of engaging in sports, camaraderie, and spiritual activity to reduce the burden that they are carrying. It was also found that social workers and peers served as primary support system during their rehabilitation. The availability of social workers and peers build trust and comfort to the CICLs. Rehabilitation process have reportedly affects the CICLs in a good way. It influenced their personal growth, companionship, and aspirations. The CICLs learned a lot of things inside the rehabilitation facility such as doing chores and waking up early. They also learned to be friendly and their aspirations gave them deeper sense of direction.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the researchers recommend the following: family visitation should be given more time given that homesickness is the most difficult challenge that the CICLs are dealing with. Regular team building should also be included in the program to foster more interaction amongst the CICLs. The faith based activities should be improved, there should be a host pastor to cater the emotional and spiritual needs of the CICLs. The social workers should be given a continuous training that will enable them to better support the needs of the CICLs. Lastly, post-rehabilitation should also be created to assist former CICLs in reintegrating into their communities and prevent reoffending.

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